

ANALYSES OF THE CONVERGENT TELCO-INSURANCE BUSINESS MODEL: MANAGERIAL PERSPECTIVES IN NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract: *The aim of the paper is to offer contribution to the national and regional theoretical and empirical framework and literature, by analyzing the aspects and factors for creation, implementation and assesment of the convergent, cross-industries joint business model, based on the open innovation model. The paper particularly analyzes the factors of the convergent Telco-insurance business model, in general, as well as for the possibilities at the national market. We focus on evolving opportunities, critical factors and managerial challenges and perspectives offered by a national survey among Telco, the insurance and the banking industry's top managers in the country. We asses them as a valuable input for current and further research focused on the perception of the changes, new value creation, managing the risks and the factors influencing the creation, initialization and performance of such a model. The paper is a part of the ongoing and broader first of a kind national academic work and empirical, qualitative and quantitative, analyses of the open innovation and synergi based convergent model.*

Keywords: *Telco industry, insurance industry, open innovation, business model, managerial perspective, survey.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The world, in an economic and socio-cultural way, has changed drastically. The only axiomatic conclusion is that the changes are intense, irreversible and continuous. All the other economic theories are under tests, thus defining the current approach in theoretical and empirical evolution assessment as dynamic and highly transformational. As no industry is left intact, the changes should be evaluated interdisciplinary and in a convergent manner. In that regard, we particularly focus on the disruptive changes and development of the convergent business model between the Telco and insurance companies, analyzing the managerial perspectives of the top managers in the telecommunication, insurance and banking industry in North Macedonia. The work is a part of the broader qualitative and quantitative analyses of the future of the open innovation based model rooted in the initial and first synergy of the Telco and insurance companies in the country. The moments of the close past linked to the disruptive consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic, related to the exponential increase of the usage of voice, data and digital platforms by the customers, are now absorbed by the new perspectives of the ongoing AI revolution. If this was previously understood as normal in the world of the Telco industry, nowadays all the rest of the industries really do not have a choice anymore. Insurers started to seize the unique and sole opportunity to capitalize on this shift. Main actions underline developement of new innovative business models with platform providers, expanding their reach and delivering value propositions to the platform customer. Amongst strong partner candidates for insurers, Telcos have always been a valuable and logical option. It is a result of their large subscriber base, strong channels, strong approach in customer profiling & analytical capabilities and digital assets with an ability to integrate customer journeys with insurance offers. The synergy gains are twofold. The Telco's continue expanding their core asset as the customers and the digital portfolios by providing financial and insurance services, throughout the proprietary platforms and strategic partnerships (Research and Markets, 2024) and the insurance companies are increasing the cost effective distribution and enhance the most important factor of selling the products and services and increasing the insurance pool in highly competitive market by nature. From the perspective of Telco's, a partnership with insurance players helps create a strong revenue stream and improve customer loyalty with a

convergence approach with insurance services supply. These evolving models are effective and are interspersed by the forms of cooperation and competition. The key opportunity is the process of the digital transformation which offers variety of broad ecosystems of diverse players that co-evolve constantly via collaboration and competition in offering industries core and additional financial services (Baumann et. al., 2023).

Both insurers and Telco's are under strong pressure to reinvent and reposition their digital businesses by possible new partnership models. The recipe for a successful insurer-telco partnership involves two key ingredients: value propositions and operating model.

Joint value propositions can be offered based on the customer's digital journeys with the Telco's, as well as by targeting specific customer segments using their behavior on the Telco's platforms. In terms of operating model, Telcos should consider being a part of a fully integrated "true partnership" model with insurers. Careful consideration is required in setting up a joint coop model and the commercial structure of a new strong partnership. A partnership will require both parties to develop new capabilities and integrate but also develop into future sustainable and open innovation business model (Chesbrough, 2006).

The paper is structured in a concise way, excluding the literature overview as there isn't adequate and vast national academic literature input for the particular open innovation model of Telco-insurance model. Among the rest, it is our motivation to fill in the gap. The first chapter is focused on the analysis of the evolution, nature and implications of the Telco and insurance industry rapid changes, as well as with the key elements of the transformation and the current and future possibilities. In the following chapter, we position the results of the conducted survey among the top managers of the Telco, insurance and banking industry in North Macedonia, followed by conclusion and future considerations.

2. TRANSFORMATIONAL CHALLENGES OF THE TELCO AND INSURANCE COMPANIES: THE JOINT MODEL FORWARD?

Telco had and are still facing the strong disruptive power of the start-ups threatening their very core. Just as free messaging platforms like WhatsApp and Instagram has killed the usage of sms as proprietary telco platform, the free calls market have been diminishing the international and roaming calls and allows evolving dominant role of the streaming platforms on tv/video market. That was the final call for the companies to open and evolve, by new approach and speed in new product development and delivery, investment efficiency and cross-industry supply. Again it always comes to the main issue: who will win the customer (PWC, 2021). Which service provider will be the one having direct interaction, contractual obligations and benefits, thus the main goal for long-term customer ownership (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Customer ownership in the Telco's industry

To win customers loyalty and strong long-term relationship, Telco must expand their ecosystems of value propositions. Moving beyond core products and services is inevitable. It is not just a matter of competitiveness, but it is also important for organic growth which is endangered (Artur D. Little, 2019). The Telco stocks' returns have been failing as the digital transformation, introduction of 5G, the process of M&A, market saturation, hypercompetitive and regulatory policies are putting high pressure on the Capex and Opex (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Returns from telco stocks versus other industries

Figure 2. Comparative industries stock returns

That defines the business strategy of new markets entrance and creating new and open business models, via strong partnership and strong collaboration with financial companies and with StartUp’s, based on the Open Innovation Model.

In parallel, the insurance industry has finally started a massive digital reorganization and adaptation to the new market environment evolution, as an increasing number of consumers are moving online. The established trends for health and life products changed the consumers demand needs, as well as the per-need-based insurance linked to the new, digitally supplied, products or service, the new risks and increased claims and the introduction of the AI in the business models, are redefining the insurers past static position. All mentioned is transforming them into the new stage of “predict and prevent” compared to the old “detect and repair” (McKinsey, 2022). Does that define safe ground for a sustainable and joint convergent Telco-insurance model? Does the new time, exponentially enhanced with AI and robotics, merge the insurance companies as the oldest big data entities and the Telcos as the economy’s and people’s highways? And how to cope with the newly expected disruptors? Clearly, there are more pros, even empirically proved, that can support the win-win game for the two industries and confirm the success of the Christensen’s theory of disruptive innovation (see Christensen, 1997) and evolution to a productive disruption. Both industries are based on the fundamentals of managing risk and leveraging data to deliver value. They have large customer base ownership. They need, posses and convert large data into structured, personalized value of products and services. They require advanced analytical systems, for predictive analytics and market churn, as the retention of the customers is of paramount importance. The issue of transferring the risk in relation to the business processes and customer cycles need’s further clarification from the time, cost and satisfaction perspective in the joint model. Since the customers are centered (Synpulse, 2024), the synergy model, in various applications, could add the new impetus to the insurance companies insufficient proactive role and support Telco’s customers risk protection in return (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Customer centered cross-industry relations

The convergence isn’t highly current model, as it isn’t a merely easy job done as someone might expect. The issues of national markets conditions, regulation and behavioral factors must be taken into consideration. However, the best possible starting model could be defined by using the ecosystem strategy (Intellias, Makarchuk, 2021). Namely, the model in which the Telcos act as orchestrators by the advantage of owning the customer relationship, digital interface, and data infrastructure, and in which the Insurers act as capability partners, providing the risk expertise, regulatory compliance, and claims management, could work

effectively. This focused, structured and joint genuine capacities and strengths, enables the development of modular, targeted and scalable services that can be competitive across the communication and insurance markets and customer segments (McKinsey, 2022).

3. MANAGERIAL PERSPECTIVES FOR THE INNOVATIVE ECOSYSTEMS AND CONVERGENT BUSINESS MODELS: THE CASE OF NORTH MACEDONIA

The following analyzes is a result of the ongoing qualitative and quantitative research for the innovative ecosystems between the Telco, insurance and banking industry, with focus on North Macedonia. The pioneering business model was established in 2022 between the largest Telco operator A1 Macedonia (part of Telekom Austria Group) and Triglav non-life insurance, a leading non-life insurance company at that time. In parallel to the rest of the vast and data quantitative analyses, at the end of 2024, we have conducted a survey, with a structured questionnaire using using Likert-type scale, with 5 level (1 = Strongly Disagree and 5 = Strongly Agree) with 60 respondents, part of the top-management structures of the Telco operators, non-life and life insurance companies and commercial banks in North Macedonia. The overall form (Q&A) is open by the authors and available upon request, as due to the lenght limitations of this paper, it could not be positioned as an appendix. Our goal was to examine top managers positions, opinions, expectations, beliefs and attitudes towards innovative behavior, convergent models, risks and crucial factors of creation, implementation and sustainability of an innovative and convergent cross-industry business model. The respondents were adequately distributed across the industries, insurance (40%), Telco (30%) and banking (30%), with high levels of education (bachelor, master, exectutive education, Ph.D) and with long term work expirience of 15+ years (70%). Their positions are within the managing and supervisory Boards, as well as at the managing positions at sales, NPD, IT, risk, marketing and strategy departments.

The questionnaire was divided into 4 main sections and consisted of 30 questions. In the first section of measuring the stands towards the intensity of changes, the respondents find the current changes in the respective industries as revolutionary. 69% of the respondents believe that the current transformations represent a *revolution* in the way industries operate, while only 31% view them as part of a slower, evolutionary process. This emphasizes the process of fundamental reconfiguration, not just incremental improvement. The vast majority of almost 90% find that the changes permanently transform the industries, that they are globally introduced rather than locally, that the main factors come both from the consumers perspectives and structural changes. They are claiming that witness and recognize the current creation of joint models and strategic partnerships between the three industries.

In the second section, dedicated to the issues of value creation, the responses are almost unanimous. 90% of the respondents believe in the business success of the joint models and strategic partnerships, as well as they find ii beneficiary for the consumers, for the growth of the industries in relation to the higher income/profit and for the competitiveness of their companies. The latter is challenging to analyze more deeply, as for the Macedonian small market, with limited Telco competition, the issues of relation between competitiveness and profitability imposes careful approach. In any case, they perceive the evolution of the current business models as convergent ones as irreversible and moreover as sustainable on the market.

In the third section, related to the perception and awareness of the risks in general, the distribution is slightly different from the first two sections. 66% of the respondents find the development and implementation of the business models burdened with high risks. In a contrary, 25% of respondents partially don't agree with that. The main risks for the respondents are: 72,9% as a result of the demand factors such as higher product complexity, lack of trust in the other industry's partner, complex process of new product acceptance/identification etc; 83,4% stresses the regulatory and supervision framework and administrative barriers; 80,9% emphasize the managerial and internal procedures allignment for the new product launch (commercialization, different organizational cultures) and 72,9% points the internal employees' resistance to change, especially to a complex new product development.

The final section determines the top managers attitudes towards the key factors for initialization, preparation and launch of the convergent business model. 58,3% think that the new model should be developed internally, in comparasion to the 29,2% that find it more sucessfull if imported from outside, one of the key issues in the model of open innovation. Evaluating the most critical factor for the introduction of the new model, the managers disperse the imporatance among the top management (33,3%), regulatory bodies (31,3%) and employees (25%). Finnally, the respondents were asked to rank the importance of offered additional 5 factors for the convergent model success, by grading each of them from 1=lowest to 5=highest importance. They put the highest importance to the vision, strategy and leadership (95,4%), followed by mutual cross-industry companies' trust (81.3%), proffitability and sustainability of the model (80,3%), human capital factor by 73% and lastly the investment with 52,1%.

As a wrap, the respondents, by 92%, expect that the convergent models would be created and operational in the following period of 1-5 years, namely 2025-2030. In that relation, the respondents find the national Telco industry as most favorable for convergent model launch (54,2%), followed by the insurance industry (25%) and banking industry (18,8%).

4. CONCLUSION

The paper aimed to contribute to the challenging academic and expert debate on the development of convergent business models based on open innovation with primary focus on the model of Telco and insurance companies, which are still rarely introduced. The motivation is high for the developing economy in North Macedonia. The theoretical findings comply to contemporary economic science. The used quantitative methodology is part of a broader and ongoing research using the primary data from the first convergent model between Telco and insurance non-life company in the national market. The paper confirms the great potential for joint business model between the two analyzed industries that can create new value propositions to the customers and enhance the classic business model. The Telcos disruptors and insurance companies' long-lasting challenges of profitability and product development, could be overcome by synergies and the adequate use of the new technologies in a single innovative model. The managerial perception and perspective for the positive outcome models of such kind are high. The perception of the key factors for such model is evolving. Currently, the managers prioritize the organizational and regulatory factors in comparison to the classic economic factors.

The limitations are present. The survey was orientated towards the top managers, excluding the human capital in the middle management that is substantial for the convergent model operation and development. The national academic participation in the process is marginal contrary to the positive cases of open innovation models across the world. The managerial perception defines the demand side as a primary one and sets less focus on responsibility and actions on the supply side in the business model development. The results of the survey are understood as a starting point for further research, on a national level, with an inter-cross industry approach, that would include the consumers and the members of the different regulatory bodies. Furthermore, the more enhanced data series of the ongoing business model will allow profound and in-depth data and business analytics, thus offering first conclusions for the pioneering Telco-insurance model in the country.

LITERATURE

- Artur D. Little. (2019). Embracing the future- How can operators embrace telecom disruption? Telecommunications industry report
- Baumann, N., Renier, J., Tang, M., French, C., & Sanchez Soriano, G. (2023). The ecosystem imperative: Digital transformation of financial services and moving from Open Banking to Open Data. Institute of International Finance (IIF) and Deloitte.
- Chesbrough, H. W. (2006). Open Innovation: The New Imperative for Creating and Profiting from Technology. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.
- Christensen, C. M. (1997). The Innovator's Dilemma
- Intellias, Roman Makarchuk. (2021). Reinventing Telcos into Data-Driven, Customer-Centric Ecosystems
- McKinsey (2022). Insurance 2030: The Impact of AI on the Future of Insurance
- PWC. (2021). Perspectives from the Global Telecom Outlook; Dr. Florian Grone, Wilson Chow, Russell Taylor
- Research and Markets. (2024). Telco, Fintech, and Insurtech Portfolio Evolution and Positioning Strategies (Report No. 6029446).
- Globe Newswire Press Release: The convergence of telecommunications, fintech, and insurtech as key driver for digital services portfolio expansion
- Synpulse. (2024). Embedded Insurance: Unlocking Opportunities for Telecom